

Ultra High Speed Approach for Document Skew Detection and Correction Based on Centre of Gravity

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Abstract : Skew detection and correction (SDC) has a direct effect in efficiency and exactitude of documents' segmentation and analysis and thus is considered as a very important step in documents' analysis field. Skew is a major problem in documents' analysis for every language. For Arabic/Persian document scripts this problem is more severe because of special features of these languages. In this paper an efficient and fast algorithm for Document Skew Detection (DSD) based on the concept of segmentation and Center of Gravity (COG) is proposed. This algorithm is examined for 150 Arabic/Persian and English documents and SDC process are done successfully for 93 percent of documents with error rate of less than 1°. This algorithm shows better results for English documents compared to Arabic/Persian documents. The proposed method is also represents favorable results for handwritten, printed and also complicated documents such as newspapers and journals even with very low quality and resolution.

Keywords : Arabic/Persian document, baseline, centre of gravity, document segmentation, skew detection and correction.

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